

Glossary of acronyms in *Representing provenance and track changes of cultural heritage metadata in RDF: a survey of existing approaches*

Acronym	Full name	Descriptive webpage
aRDF	annotated RDF	https://doi.org/10.1145/1656242.1656245
DC	Dublin Core	https://www.dublincore.org/
OCDM	OpenCitations Data Model	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-62466-8_28
OPM	Open Provenance Model	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2010.07.005
OWL	Web Ontology Language	https://www.w3.org/OWL/
PaCE	Provenance Context Entity	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-13818-8_32
PML	Proof Markup Language	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.is.2005.02.003
PREMIS	PREservation Metadata: Implementation Strategies	https://www.loc.gov/standards/premis/understanding-premis-rev2017.pdf
PROV-O	Provenance Ontology	https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/
RDF	Resource Description Framework	https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf11-concepts/
RDFS	RDF Schema	https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-schema/
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language	https://www.w3.org/TR/sparql11-query/
SPOTL(X)	Subject Predicate Object Time Location (Context)	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.artint.2012.06.001
SWAN	Semantic Web Applications in Neuromedicine	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbi.2008.04.010
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium	https://www.w3.org/